

A Study of Price Discovery of Rubber Futures Market in India

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Abstract

The study analyses price discovery function of Rubber market of National Multi Commodity Exchange (NMCE) for the period 01/01/2015 to 31/7/2017. After identifying single co integrating vector, VECM is used to analyze long run and short run causality of rubber. The evidence shows that for there is a unidirectional causal relationship from future to spot market in long run. Granger Causality test shows that a future price leads the spot prices. The study revealed the efficiency of futures market in performing price discovery function

Keywords: Price Discovery, Rubber, Cointegration, VECM, Granger Causality

INTRODUCTION

Rubber is a polymer consisting of hydrogen and carbon and is elastic in nature. It is found in the fluid of some specific plants but it can also be produced synthetically. Naturally, rubber is produced by the process of tapping of the plant called *Hevea Brasiliensis*. These plants generally have 32 years of economic life but they may live upto 100 years or even more than that. Synthetic rubber is produced through the process of polymerization of various monomers. The basic property of rubber is that it comes back to its original shape if it is twisted or stretched but if heat is applied to the rubber, it won't return to its original shape easily. Rubber is found in two varieties – Natural Latex and Natural Rubber.

- Natural Latex is referred to a fluid, white in color, which is attained from rubber tree. It comprises of small rubber particles and plant proteins.
- Natural Rubber is produced with the help of either of the two processes – Natural Rubber Latex process (NRL) or Dry Natural Rubber process (DNR) and it includes all the products made from latex.

The rubber industry produces wide range products like auto tyres, auto tubes, automobile parts, footwear, belts, cables & wires, battery boxes etc. Block rubber, Preserved Latex, Crepes Etc.

Futures trading of rubber commenced on NMCE in March 2003. It has helped in better price discovery and price risk management to the stakeholders of rubber. In the peak season, due to excess supply spot rubber price used to become very low and farmers had no alternative but to

sell at that low price. But now with the NMCE futures market they have alternative market where they can sell at higher price for future date delivery. Though rubber is a compulsory delivery contract the stakeholders are required to make delivery only if they have open position. If they have settled their sell and buy position and have no obligation open then they can simply hedge their price risk and need not undertake the burden or extra cost of delivery. Threat of delivery allows the futures market and spot market to converge on the date of settlement of the contract.

If the future price would be higher then there is incentive to the producers to sell and deliver on the Exchange. On the contrary if futures price was lower than spot market traders and processors would take delivery from the Exchange till price gets aligned to the spot market. When the future price is higher than spot price the market is said to be in 'contango'. In peak season when there is excessive supply, such situations always arise, which was problematic for the producers but now with NMCE futures market the farmers are not compelled to sell in the spot market and benefit by selling on NMCE futures market. In off-season market reverses and the spot price becomes higher than the future price, market then is said to be in 'backwardation'. At that time the farmers and traders buy back their NMCE futures position at lower price and sell their rubber in the spot market at higher price. This way they take benefit of both the market situation; one when the supply is excess and other when there is shortage in the supply.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nambiar and Balasubramaniam (2016) analysed the price behaviour in Spot and Future market for Rubber, to examine the efficiency of price discovery in Indian Rubber market and to compare the price discovery during pre recession and post recession. For this purpose daily price data of rubber futures and spot markets were collected during the year 2004-2014 and analyzed, using descriptive mean, variance and Vector Auto Regression model. The study reveals that during the post recession period the Rubber futures play its inherent function of price discovery. So the participants in the market can trust futures market prices to predict the spot price movements.

Iyer and Pillai (2010) examined whether futures markets play a dominant role in the price discovery process. The rate of convergence of information from one market to another is also analyzed to infer the efficiency of futures as an effective hedging tool. The paper finds evidence for price discovery process happening in the futures market in five out of six commodities. However, the rate of convergence of information is slow, particularly in the non-expiration weeks. For copper, gold and silver, the rate of convergence is almost instantaneous during the expiration week of the futures contract affirming the utility of futures contracts as an effective hedging tool. In case of chickpeas, nickel and rubber the convergence worsens during the expiration week indicating the non-usability of futures contract for hedging

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To analyze the price discovery the price discovery process of rubber future and spot price contracts

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The sample period for the study is from 01/01/2015 to 31/07/2017. Daily closing prices of rubber futures and spot market are taken from the website of NMCE. The analysis has been done through Eviews7 software. The study used Augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF Test) to check the Stationarity of data. The long-term relationship between futures and spot price is found out using Cointegration technique. Short run integration between Spot and futures market are analyzed through Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The granger causality test is applied to examine the lead lag relationship between spot and futures market.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Augmented Dickey Fuller test

Before testing for cointegration, the time series must be checked for stationarity. The stationarity properties and exhibition of unit roots in the time series are substantiated by performing Augmented Dickey Fuller tests. This test is conducted on the variables in original price series and first differences. The variables that are integrated in the same order may be co integrated, while the unit root tests find out which variables are integrated of same order, for example; if integrated by order one, which is denoted as $I(1)$. The results of ADF test are presented in the table below.

Table 1: Results of ADF tests

The result shows that all the variables are non-stationary at level. But they are found to be

	Spot at level	Spot at 1st differencing	Futures at level	Futures at 1st differencing
<i>ADF test statistic</i>	-1.676166	-17.17280	-1.920258	-26.62431
<i>P Value</i>	0.4430	0.0000	0.3230	0.0000
<i>Integration</i>	I(1)		I(1)	

stationary at their first difference. Therefore, necessary condition for cointegration is satisfied

Johansen's Cointegration Test

To analyze the nature of long-run relationship between spot and the futures market for rubber futures market, Johansen's cointegration test is performed. One of the preconditions for using the cointegration test is that the data must be stationary at first difference and not at levels. The results of cointegration tests are presented in the table 2.

Table 2: Johansen's cointegration test results

	Vector(r)	Trace Statistics(λ_{trace})	Maximal Eigen Value(λ_{max})	5% Critical Value for Trace Statistics	5% Critical Value for Max.Eigen Statistics	Remarks
Rubber	$H_0 \text{ } r=0$	65.65086	61.34732	15.49471	14.26460	Cointegrated
	$H_1 \text{ } r \geq 1$	4.303535	4.303535	3.841466	3.841466	

The results reveal that there is at most 1 cointegrating equation between the variables. Both trace statistics and maximum Eigen values support the presence of cointegration. So, it has been concluded that there is long run equilibrium relationship between spot and future of rubber.

Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

The cointegration criterion, if validated, facilitates the error correction model. The model has been used to identify the market where price discovery occurs. The analysis reveals that there is cointegrating relationship between future and spot prices of Rubber. So we further proceed to develop vector error correction model to analyze the price discovery process.

Table 3: VECM test results

	L Spot Prices				L Future Prices			
	Coefficient	S.E	t-statistic	p.value	Coefficient	S.E	t-statistic	p.value
c	-0.01318	4.237605	-0.00311	0.9975	0.675955	8.8818	0.07611	0.939
ΔS_{t-1}	0.01832	0.051300	0.35710	0.7211	-0.17856	0.1075	-1.6607	0.097
ΔS_{t-2}	0.14486	0.044042	3.28925	0.0011	0.18655	0.0923	2.0208	0.043
ΔF_{t-1}	0.16479	0.029268	5.63065	0.0000	0.05941	0.0613	0.96861	0.333
ΔF_{t-2}	0.03542	0.025625	1.38238	0.1673	0.03683	0.0537	0.68575	0.493
ECT	-0.09265	0.020857	-4.44226	0.0000	-0.08616	0.0461	-1.86542	0.062

From the above table it can be seen that the error correction term for spot prices is negative and significant on the other hand, the error correction term of future prices is negative and

insignificant. So it can be concluded that the price discovery of rubber is happening in futures market and any disequilibrium in short run is corrected by spot market.

Granger Causality Test

With the prerequisite of testing stationary done, the widely-accepted Granger causality test is deployed to detect the direction of relationship between two variables (Granger, 1969). The results of granger causality test are reported in table 4.

Table 4: Granger Causality Test results

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F Statistic	P.Value
Future prices does not granger cause spot prices	633	43.7868	0.000
Spot prices does not granger cause future prices		0.55726	0.5731

From the table it can be seen that the Null hypothesis “Future price does not granger causes spot prices” is rejected as the p value is found to be less than 5%. But we fail to reject the null hypothesis “Spot prices does not granger causes Future prices”. This shows that the future prices lead the spot prices and past values of future prices can be used to predict future spot prices of rubber.

CONCLUSION

Johansen’s cointegration test along with VECM is applied to test the price discovery process of rubber traded in National Multi Commodity Exchange (NMCE) for the period 01/01/2015 to 31/07/2017. The empirical analysis was done on the daily time series during the period. Using ADF test, it was found that all the variables are stationary at their first difference. Johansen’s Cointegration test revealed there is a long run equilibrium relationship between the futures and spot prices. Vector Error correction model is applied to find out the speed of adjustment in case of disequilibrium in short run. The granger causality test is applied to understand the lead lag relationship between the variables. The study showed that future and spot prices are integrated in long run. The new information is first reflected in future market and any deviation from equilibrium in long run is corrected by spot market. In granger causality test also shows the dominance of future market, where future prices leads while spot prices lags. Thus in rubber market, price discovery function is performed by rubber futures market and can be used to predict the respective future spot prices.

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